

The Influence of Leadership on Followers Performance among Bottle Water Companies in Port Harcourt

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ABSTRACT

This study was to investigate the relationship between leadership style and followers performance in the bottle water companies in port Harcourt. In this study, we have two variables leadership style as the independent variable and followers performances as the dependent variable, the methodology adopted were descriptive research design to collect both primary and secondary data. The population of this study consists of 100 (one hundred) employees in the selected bottle water companies in Port Harcourt. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire in four point likert scale. 100 copies of questionnaire were distributed to employees of selected bottle water companies in Port Harcourt which 90 was retrieved for the analysis. From the above it was discovered that leadership styles have a positive impact on the followers, but each have to be used strategically in different environment in other to maximize employees performance. It was recommended that organizations should empower and motivate employees since this will ensure total loyalty and increase their retention and productivity to the organization.

Keywords-- Leadership, Performance, Organization, Followers, Companies, Total Loyalty and Motivation Employees, Productivity

I. INTRODUCTION

The relation between leadership behaviours and follower performance is one of the oldest and most widely researched topics in organizational behavior (e.g., Stogdill, 1950; Yukl, 2012). Generally, the debate has been on whether leader behaviors increases follower performance and the degree to which they do so across different types of leadership behaviors and follower performance. The function of leadership in an organization is essential in terms of crafting a vision, mission, determination and establishment of objectives, scheming strategies, policies, and methods to achieve the organizational objectives effectively and efficiently along with directing and coordinating the efforts and organizational activities (Xu & Wang, 2008). To Xu and Wang this are the basic role a leader must do in other to improve organizational performance . The concept of Leadership is increasingly assumed to encompass persuasion and explanation and also the ability to

identify, affirm, and renew the values of the group the leader represents. Thus, it has been observed that managerial expertise,, cultural literacy, technical skills, and other relevant knowledge and skills are considered not adequate for the leaders whose lives will be dedicated to public services. A leader is said to be effective when he / she recognizes that he has a responsibility to provide guide and share their knowledge to their followers to lead them for better performance and make them skilful for maintaining the quality. Thus, becoming head of all team members is such a great responsibility. Top quality leadership is essential to achieve the mission and vision along with coping with the changes occurring in the external environment. Nowadays, many enterprises are facing challenges related to unethical practices, high labour turnover, poor financial performance, etc. Thus ,as a result of lack of effective leadership.

However, it has been observed that most of the research work done on leadership are confusing the definition of effective leadership by failing to make clear distinctions between leaders and non-leaders, effective and ineffective leaders (House and Aditya, 1997; Bennis, 1998; Bergsteiner, 2005). In spite of this, it is widely understood that leadership fosters employee performance at organisational level (Avolio, 1999; Yukl, 2002; Judge and Piccolo, 2004; Keller, 2006). Furthermore, majority of the past research has examined the assumed leadership-performance relationship, although tested limited number of leadership approaches such as visionary and transactional while ignoring the potential role of other approaches such as classical and organic paradigms of leadership (Jing and Avery, 2008). One of the popular model of leadership theory criticised was Bass's (1985) theory of transformational leadership and maintained that there is no one best way of leadership to be effective, where it depends on context (Avery, 2004; Drath, 2001).This actually suggest that managers as leaders should have or consider a mix of leadership skill or method so as to improve their followers performance .

Statement of Problem

Some major variables of ascertaining a follower or a worker performance includes executing defined duties, meeting deadlines, competency, and effectiveness and efficiency in doing work. Every business enterprises needs strong leadership styles that will arouse the employee performance. While some firms such as

bottling factory face the problems of : poor innovation, low productivity, inability to meet performance targets. This challenges was as a result of lack of strategic interventions of specific leadership styles to the particular situations was projected as the problem at hand. This problem was continuously affecting followers or employees performance. This is the reason why this research are being conducted to investigates the best leadership style that stimulates performance of individuals in the organization .

It is believed that an effective organization is embedded on the business leaders. The idea of effective leadership is also adopted in the world of technology. In every business organization the followers or employees most at times likewise perceived that there is a need for them to have an exemplary figure as a leader who should not only have to lead them but also be effective. So, they need an effective leader who can lead them towards the changes and performance improvement. This study therefore aims to study the influence of leadership on followers performance among bottle water companies in port Harcourt using the different style of leadership such as democratic, autocratic, participative and transactional leadership style.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the effect of democratic leadership style on followers performance in bottle water companies in port Harcourt.
2. To find out the relationship between autocratic leadership style on followers performance in bottle water companies in port Harcourt.
3. To examine the effect of participative leadership style on followers performance in bottle water companies in port Harcourt.
4. To examine the effect of transactional leadership style on followers performance in bottle water companies in port Harcourt.

Literature Review

Concept of leadership

Leadership is an ability of a manager to induce the subordinates to work with confidence and zeal.

Leadership can be defined as the capacity to influence a group realization of the goal.

Leadership is a process –to influence others, and leadership occurs in groups-involve in achieving common goals and purpose (Northouse, 2010). As a process it involves channelling peoples effort to achieve a common goal. Therefore Northouse (2010, p.3) define leadership as ‘a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal’. This is very parallel to the definition of Robbins (2006) who saw leadership as the capacity to influence a group to achieve the desired goal set by a leader. In contrast, more generally leadership is the ability of an individual to utilize the influence of an organisation or situation to achieve challenging goals (Ivansevich, 2008). Some scholars have viewed leadership is a process that exercises the power owned by an individual through position, expertise, proficiency or charisma to influence employees in an organisation to achieve a desired goal (Kelloway & Barling, 2010).

Theoretical Perspective

The Fred Fiedler presents the theory of Fiedler leadership contingency model theory in which he proposed that effective employees performance depended upon the proper match between a leaders’ ability to lead is contingent upon situational factors that include the leaders’ capabilities, preferred style, and behaviour, competency of employees [fisher 1995]. This theory advocated that leaders should utilize that style which best suit the situation and immediately stimulate the employee performance.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Population of the Study

Population is a set of object or observations about which conclusion are drawn. The population of the study is 100 staff members which includes top level employees, middle level employees and low level employees. The amount of analysis is at the micro level and thus individual based.

Table 3.1 Classes of the Target Population

Category	ODION TABLE WATER	ICE LAND TABLE WATER	JUNAC TABLE WATER	Total
Top level employees	10	10	3	33
Middle level employees	2	3	1	6
Low level employees	25	15	11	71
Total	27	28	15	100

Source: (Field survey, 2019)

Sampling Techniques

The sampling techniques that will be utilized in the research work is random sampling with a total

population size 100 staff which will be used to compare their opinion in the company.

Method of Data Collection

The central of every research is to proffer a solution to the identified problems of the subject of study, which can only be achieved through the collection of reliable data. In this research work, method of data collection will be both primary and secondary sources.

Primary Source of Data

These are first-hand information for the purpose of this project. These studies make use of the questionnaire and oral interview as a major source of primary data.

Secondary Source of data

This information already in existence, having been collected originally for some other purposes. They includes the reviewing of articles that have to do with creativity, innovation and current journal, textbooks, Newspaper and internet , magazine ,textbooks etc.

Research Instrument

The research instrument for this study will be the questionnaire. According to Ojo (2005) questionnaire is an instrument containing some questions and statements (some with suggested alternative answers) for which the questions or confirm the statements. The questionnaire that will be used in the study will be divided in two sections. Section A contained information about the respondents that is their gender, marital status, age, educational qualification, years of working experience etc. Section B contained items on the leadership and followers performance. The second section that will be ranged from 5-1 point scale in the following pattern,

strongly agree: 5, Agree: 4 undecided: 3, Disagree: 2 and Strongly Disagree: 1.

Validity of the Research Instrument

A number of concepts are involved in a discussion of validity. Different types of validity have been identified. These include, the predictive validity which is the validity of an instrument to predict some future events, the concurrent validity which is usually measured by the calculation of a correction coefficient between the distribution of test scores and some concurrently existing criterion measure, the content validity which is essentially determined by the process through which the items were selected.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics which includes frequencies, mean, standard deviation. Data collected was reported using frequency tables.

III. RESULTS

The chapter presents data pertinent to the research questions and objective formulated to guide the study.

Findings and Data Analysis**Gender of Respondents**

The study involved gender distribution of respondents in order to answer the questionnaires provided as shown on the table.

Table 3.1: Gender of Respondents

Respondents	frequencies	Percentage %
Female	20	22.22
Male	70	77.77
Total	90	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2019

Table 3.1 above depicts that 80% and 20 % of respondents of male and female respectively answered the questionnaires distributed .

The study involved gender distribution of respondents in order to answer the questionnaires provided as shown on the table.

Table 3.2: Gender of Respondents

Respondents	Frequency	Percent %
Single	20	22.22
Married	70	77.77
Divorced	0	0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2019

Table 3.2 above depicts that 77.77% and 22.22 % of respondents of single and married respectively answered the questionnaires distribute.

Table 3.3: Educational Qualification Level of Respondents

Respondents	Frequency	Percent %
BS.C/HND	55	61.11
Master	25	27.77

Others	10	11.11
Total	90	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2019

The others group constituted 11.11% of respondents, followed by master with 22.77% and then the BS.C which made up 61.11% of the respondents.

Table 4.4: Year of Experience

Respondents	Frequency	Percent %
5-10years	15	16.66
10--15years	25	27.27
15-20years	40	50
20-30 years	10	11.11
Total	90	100.0

Source: Researcher, 2019

The 5-10 years of experiences constituted 16.66% of respondents, followed by 10-15 years within the range of 27.27% and then the range of 15-20 years of experiences which made up 50% of the respondents. The lowest number of respondents was within the range of 20-30 years which made 11.11% of employees.

Research question 1: To what extent does democratic leadership style relate to followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt

Table 3.1: Mean and Standard Deviation for Democratic leadership style on followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt

S/NO	Statement	X	STD	RMK
1	Leader share responsibility among staff	3.34	0.87	A
2	Allows delegation of function	3.20	0.76	A
3	Allows staff consultation before taking decision	3.40	0.84	SA
4	Allows innovative idea	3.04	0.85	A

Table 3.1 revealed that democratic leadership style range from 3.04-3.34 and standard deviation of 0.76-0.87. They all agreed to a high extent on the impact of democratic style of leadership style on followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt.

Research question 2: To what extent does autocratic leadership style relate to followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt?

Table 3.2: Mean and Standard Deviation for autocratic leadership style in followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt

S/NO	Statement	X	STD	RMK
1	No suggestion is welcome from employee	3.50	0.87	A
2	Fill demotivated	3.40	0.85	A
3	Work under pressure	3.20	0.84	SA
4	Deadline and target are set	3.50	0.76	A

Table 3.2 revealed that autocratic leadership style range from 3.20-3.50 and standard deviation of 0.76-0.87. They all agreed to a high extent on the impact

of autocratic leadership style in followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt.

Research question 3: To what extent does participative leadership style relate followers performance in bottle

water producers in port Harcourt.

Table 3.3: Mean and Standard Deviation for participative leadership style related to followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt .

S/NO	Statement	X	STD	RMK
1	Allows employees to take decision on how to perform their job	3.30	0.76	A
2	I have good communication with my colleagues at work	3.50	0.84	SA
3	Staff empowerment is encouraged	3.20	0.83	A
4	I manager my time at work place effectively and efficiently	3.10	0.83	A

Table 3.3 revealed that participative leadership style range from 3.10-3.50 and standard deviation of 0.76-0.84. They all agreed to a high extent on the impact participative leadership style in followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt .

Research question 4: To what extent does Transactional leadership style relate followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt.

Table 3.4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Transactional leadership style related followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt

S/NO	Statement	X	STD	RMK
1	I am giving a reward after I accomplish my job	3.02	0.87	A
2	I am giving recognition any time target is achieve	3.24	0.76	A
3	I am innovative in carrying out my job	3.40	0.83	A
4	My job is monitored to ensure error free	3.50	0.82	A

Table 3.4 revealed that the transactional leadership style range from 3.02-3.50 and standard deviation of 0.76-0.87. They all agreed to a high extent on the impact of transactional leadership style on followers performance in bottle water producers in port Harcourt.

IV. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDING

The study sought to examine the relationship between leadership and followers Performance in bottle water companies in port Harcourt .Employees in the organization want to be valued and appreciated for their effort towards the achievement of the business goal and objectives . A good leadership style is all it takes to motivate followers towards higher job performance, especially workers from production and construction companies where task of the employees we will admit are stressful most at time .

The study found out that, there is a significant difference in Democratic leadership style on followers performance in bottle water companies in port Harcourt.

The study also found out that there is a significant difference in Democratic leadership style and followers innovativeness in bottle water companies in port Harcourt . Moreover, there are other non-leadership style factors that have a positive influence on leadership , such as belief system ,company culture, education and personality. It was observed that employee motivation and empowerment are keys in job performance .this

leadership style tends to or has the ability to enhance follower's motivation and foster interpersonal communication. Nevertheless, studies have shown that adopting the participating leadership style where followers are carried along and are allowed to make decisions and contributions boost productivity on the long term and also better rewards improve job performance significantly (Rukmani, et al., 2010). The study also found that there is a significant difference in autocratic leadership style and creativity of employees or followers in bottle water companies in Port Harcourt.

It was observed that autocratic leadership style leads to followers or employees job dissatisfaction, which in turn influences negatively the performance of employees or follower. Although, autocratic style has been used in some cases to achieve a goal but it tends to discourage the theory of empowerment and decreases the possibility of employees retention and decreases their effectiveness. The study conversely also found that there is a significant difference in participative leadership style and followers performance in bottle water companies in port Harcourt. It was observed that high level of productivity is influenced by the level of communication and empowerment. Therefore, developing and implementing a sound communication between managers and their employees and allowing them to take certain decision on their task improves job performance and individual productivity . Further, the study found that there is a significant difference in transactional leadership style and followers performance in bottle water

companies in Port Harcourt. It was noticed that this style of leadership promotes recognition of employees thus encourages constant motivation which increases job performance in this is very essential for an organization that wants to be successful. Furthermore it was observed that when employee's task is supervised it reduces their error rate and increases their performance. This style of leadership instills seriousness and concentration on followers in carrying out a task which leads to increase productivity.

It was observed that transactional leadership style increase the level of follower's job performance in bottle water companies in Port Harcourt. Although, over the years many of these companies have use pay, promotion, bonuses and other types of reward as motivation to their employees and to increase their job performance. In order for leadership to be used as a motivational tool to increase their followers or employees job performance, managers have to investigate the leadership style that will best suit the type of organization, the environment and level of their followers' awareness. Thus, the style of leadership will determines how the followers' performance will be, since Employees can also be motivated through proper leadership, as leadership involves getting things done the right way.

V. CONCLUSION

This study has focused on the impact of leadership styles on organizational performance. Leadership plays a vital role in followers performance in bottle water companies in port Harcourt. while there has been a significant amount of research aimed at identifying why leadership behaviours lead to follower performance. Considering our analysis it was discovered that that followers performance is associated with the leadership style and they have both a positive and a negative impact on the performance. While the democratic , autocratic , participative and transactional leadership style have a positive influence ,it is worth nothing that the managers should consider some factors such as level of employees exposure , organizational environment, organizational culture and tasks involves in completion of a task before adopting a particular leadership style. However, If employees feel appreciated when they are working or under a leader who motivate them and appreciates their effort for job performance, involved them in decision-making process , and communicate well with them this in turn enhances enthusiasm and motivation which often lead to better productivity and loyalty from the employees. The study therefore, concludes that all the leadership style improves employees or followers performance, however, should be adopted in peculiar time when specific objective and goal is expected or need to be achieved . Thus this is to be able to increase followers or employees performance.

RECOMMENDATION

From the findings, the following recommendation was stated below:

1. The study recommends that motivation of employees will ensure total loyalty and increase their retention and productivity to the organization.
2. Managers should use each of the style or combination of it in specific environment. Since one of the leadership style is considered best but looking at the environment of the organization to see the one that will facilitate the achievement of organizational objective.
3. Employees empowerment should be adopted, this often serves as motivation, it also helps in increasing employees performance.
4. To continuously improve followers performance, a sound communication and feed back mechanism should be established. While this increases performance it also brings the leader closer to his subject .

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